

Applying CoARA Principles in the CNR Senior Researcher Competition: A Comparative and Critical Analysis Across Disciplinary Areas

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a comparative and critical documentary analysis of the evaluation criteria adopted in the CNR Senior Researcher competition considering CoARA principles. It integrates a descriptive assessment of the structure of the criteria with a critical examination of their implementation across the 35 disciplinary areas.

The results reveal a shared conceptual framework, alongside significant variability in practical application. In particular, the analysis highlights differences in the use of bibliometric indicators, the recognition of non-traditional research outputs, and the internal consistency of evaluation procedures.

Humanities and social sciences generally show stronger alignment with content-based and qualitative evaluation approaches, whereas scientific and technological areas tend to combine broader output recognition with a more structured use of journal-based indicators. These findings suggest that disciplinary contexts play a key role in shaping how general principles of responsible research assessment are interpreted and operationalized.

Future work should integrate outcome-based validation.

Keywords: CoARA; research assessment; CNR; senior researcher competition; disciplinary differences; qualitative evaluation; responsible metrics.

INTRODUCTION

The international debate on research assessment increasingly stresses the need to move beyond narrow proxy indicators and adopt qualitative, contextual, and responsible evaluation practices. Within this framework, CoARA promotes the abandonment of inappropriate metrics such as Journal Impact Factor or h-index as primary evaluation tools, emphasizing peer review and content-based judgment.

The CNR senior Researcher competition represents a relevant case study, as it was launched after the institution formally adhered to CoARA. While the structure of the call reflects these principles, their practical implementation across the 35 disciplinary areas shows a complex and sometimes contradictory picture.

Beyond variability, several distortions emerge:

- penalization of multidisciplinary and applied contributions
- undervaluation of technical-scientific support activities
- persistence of metric-based biases
- excessive discretionary or “open” evaluation frameworks, which paradoxically may lead to mechanical scoring practices rather than richer qualitative judgment
- evaluation criteria were defined after the call deadline, instead declaring those requirements in advance

Figure 1. Comparative framework for assessing CoARA alignment

The figure summarizes the documentary analysis workflow, from the official competition documents to the comparative interpretation of assessment criteria across disciplinary areas. It highlights the distinction between humanities/social sciences and scientific/technological areas, which is central to the analysis.

The analysis does not aim to evaluate the adequacy of the institutional framework itself, but rather to examine how general principles are interpreted and implemented across disciplinary contexts.

METHODS

The study is based on documentary analysis of official evaluation criteria across five sections:

1. Products and titles
2. Scientific contribution and results
3. Scientific perspective and potential
4. Professional path
5. Interview

The analysis also incorporates a statistical-comparative approach (derived from the Italian draft) examining:

- variability (min–max scores)
- quartile distribution (Q1, median, Q3)
- presence of outliers

This enables identification of convergence patterns and distortive tendencies across areas. Section 1 represents the most significant weighting pillar of the entire competition: with a maximum of 45 points, and a ceiling of 3 points per submitted item, it decisively influences the outcome of the selection.

Tables 1 show the classifications into products and titles.

Table 1 - Types of Research Outputs (P1–P11)

Code	Type of Output	Code	Type of Output
P1	Journal articles	T1	Project leadership
P2	Book chapters	T2	Excavation leadership
P3	Books / monographs	T3	Infrastructure responsibility
P4	Conference proceedings and posters	T4	Project participation
P5	Patents	T5	Excavation participation
P6	Databases, software, datasets	T6	Infrastructure participation
P7	Projects and prototypes	T7	Research group leadership
P8	Exhibitions and displays	T8	Research appointments
P9	Cartographic products and maps	T9	Institute direction
P10	Indexes, bibliographies, commentaries	T10	Teaching roles
P11	Technical reports	T11	Evaluation committees
		T12	Scientific associations leadership
		T13	Technical-scientific bodies
		T14	Journal direction
		T15	Conference coordination
		T16	Editorial boards
		T17	ERC and awards
		T18	Invited lectures
		T19	Consultancy roles
		T20	Scientific diplomacy
		T21	Certification activities
		T22	Start-ups/spin-offs
		T23	Outreach activities
		T24	Internal management roles
		T25	Professional organizational roles
		T26	National Scientific Qualification
		T27	PhD supervision

The study of the scores assigned to the different products for the PR competition was analyzed using the resulting variability (between maximum and minimum) for all disciplinary areas, as well as the distribution described by 25% (first quartile - Q1), 50% (Median), and 75% (third quartile - Q3) of the scores assigned for each product. While the range between Q1 and Q3 of the scores assigned by each commission is an indicator of the agreement in recognizing the value of the product or category, the median identifies the propensity of criteria adopted in some areas to reward certain types rather than others certain types rather than others. Outliers are those scores that statistically differ from many scores assigned to each individual product by the commissions (Figure 2)

Figure 2 - Distribution of scores assigned to different types of research outputs (P1–P11).

Boxplots represent the variability across the 35 disciplinary areas in the CNR senior Researcher competition. Each box shows the interquartile range (Q1–Q3), with the median indicated by a horizontal line. Whiskers denote minimum and maximum values, excluding outliers, which are shown as individual points.

For interpretive purposes, the disciplinary areas were considered in two broad families: humanities/social sciences and scientific/technological areas. This was not done to reduce complexity, but to make visible broad patterns in the application of assessment criteria. The comparison was then interpreted in relation to several CoARA-oriented principles, including the responsible use of metrics, the recognition of diverse research outputs, the

avoidance of inappropriate proxy indicators, and the preference for contextual and qualitative judgment [web:6]. The analysis is therefore descriptive, comparative, and documentary, rather than statistical in the strict inferential sense.

In Figure 3 reports the statistical distribution of scores to commissions for each type of title.

Figure 3 - Statistical distribution of scores assigned to commissions for each type of title

RESULTS

Section 1: Products and Titles

The analysis of Section 1 shows a common general structure, but also substantial heterogeneity in how the areas assigned value to different types of output and titles. Across many areas, journal articles remain central, but the basis for evaluating them varies significantly, creating a hybrid assessment culture where responsible recognition of diverse outputs coexists with persistent reliance on journal-based proxies. This variation is especially visible when comparing scientific areas with humanities-oriented areas.

In the humanities and social sciences, the criteria often reflect stronger attention to the nature of the output rather than only the container in which it appears. Books, monographs,

critical editions, source editions, and scientific commentaries frequently receive substantial recognition, sometimes equal to or higher than those assigned to journal articles. This pattern is consistent with the publication ecology of these fields, in which books and long-form scholarly contributions play a central role.

In several areas, editorial quality is assessed through concepts such as scientific series, editorial boards, or national classification schemes rather than through citation-based metrics. This indicates a more direct alignment with CoARA's emphasis on content and context.

In the scientific and technological areas, the picture is more mixed. On the one hand, there is clear recognition of a wider range of outputs, including patents, software, databases, datasets, and in some cases prototypes or technical reports. This is a positive feature from a CoARA perspective, because it broadens the scope of what counts as research contribution.

On the other hand, several areas still give strong weight to journal rank, quartile position, or citation-related information. In some cases, these indicators remain central to the definition of quality, leading to a direct clash with modern evaluation principles:

In several areas, journal-based indicators and bibliometric information appear in a more structured role than recommended by CoARA, reflecting differences in interpretation across disciplinary contexts.

A recurring pattern is the assignment of null or very low scores to certain categories of non-conventional outputs, particularly in some disciplinary areas of prototypes (P7), maps (P9), and technical reports (P11) in "pure" academic areas such as 03, 07, 11, 13, 14, and 15. This appears only partially consistent with the spirit of the call to value technological impact and technical-scientific support, neutralizing the progress made in broadening the scope of research outputs.

The role of the author and the evaluation of co-authorship also vary sharply across areas, producing uneven treatment across product types.

While some areas adopted more qualitative scales based on relevance, originality, impact, and the author's role—treating author position and individual contribution as important—others appeared to penalize or overlook these factors:

Penalization of Collaboration: Area 03 and 29 introduced a "bonus" for a limited number of authors, a mechanical restriction that may disadvantage highly collaborative and multidisciplinary research and multidisciplinary research.

Devaluation of Individual Contribution: For "non-conventional" products, the candidate's specific role was entirely ignored in 80% of the sectors, reducing the overall relevance of the author's actual input.

From a CoARA-oriented viewpoint, the most robust practices remain those that qualitatively assess the candidate's specific contribution without mechanically privileging a narrow authorship pattern or relying strictly on the container over the content.

In Figure 4 the frequency of the number of judging components selected by the commissions for each product type was reported.

Figure 4 - the frequency of the number of judging components selected by the commissions for each product type

The stacked percentage chart illustrates how different evaluation areas distributed the "weight" or number of criteria (represented by the categories '0', '1-2', '3-4', '>4') when judging eleven distinct types of research outputs (P1 to 11).

The analysis shows three fundamental trends that highlight a deep rift between "traditional" and "non-conventional" research products.

- The Absolute Centrality of Traditional Products (P1 - P4). Products P1, P2, P3, and P4 (typically journal articles, monographs, book chapters, and

conference proceedings) exhibit the lowest percentage of the `0` value (the dark blue bar).

P1 is the most meticulously regulated output: nearly 85% of the areas apply 3 or more evaluation criteria (`3-4` or ` >4 `), and the share of areas that completely ignore it is minimal (under 20%).

This block demonstrates that the evaluation framework remains firmly anchored to classical scientific production, where committees deploy highly articulated and complex grids of criteria.

- The Transition Zone (P5 - P6). Products P5 and P6 represent a middle ground. Here, the number of areas that completely zero out the evaluation (`0`) rises drastically, fluctuating between 50% and 60%. However, for the areas that do choose to evaluate these products, there is still a noticeable effort toward structured assessment (a significant presence of the orange `1-2` and green `3-4` bands), signaling an open debate or a partial transition toward their recognition.
- The problematic reliance on proxies of Non-Conventional Products (P7 - P11). The most striking finding in the chart is the overwhelming dominance of the dark blue bar (`0`) for products P7 through P11 (which include prototypes, maps, technical reports, datasets, and software).

On average, between 65% and 80% of the scientific areas assign a score of zero or provide no criteria at all for these outputs. The peak is reached in P10, where nearly 80% of the areas completely ignore the product.

In the rare instances where these products are taken into consideration, their assessment is almost exclusively left to a very limited number of criteria (prevalence of the orange `1-2` band over the green one).

Here is the integrated text in English, combined into a continuous narrative without subheadings as requested.

Section 2: contribution and results of activity

Section 2 represents the central component of the curricular evaluation, allocating 25 points to a reasoned judgment on the candidate's ability to drive significant advancements in the interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary knowledge of the Institution. This assessment is structured around the three dimensions outlined in the call: advancing the frontiers of research, valorization of results, and technical-scientific support and dissemination. The analysis of the specific criteria adopted across disciplinary areas indicates five recurring models, each carrying distinct assumptions about how best to assess scientific merit and differing implications for their alignment with the call. The Quantitative-Qualitative Model (Areas 01, 10, 12, 17, 24) defines explicit criteria with a predefined qualitative scale (Excellent = 25, Very Good = 20, Good = 15) and fully integrates multidisciplinary as an explicit fourth evaluation dimension. The Career and CNR Coherence Focused Model (Areas 03, 05, 13, 18, 19, 26, 31, 34) instead emphasizes professional history and alignment with the Institution's missions, placing the strategic contribution to the CNR at the center. The Quantitative Distribution Model (Areas 04, 30) introduces fixed internal weights that limit the committee's evaluative freedom, while the Individual Contribution Focused Model (Areas 15, 21, 22, 27) aims to isolate the candidate's specific qualitative impact. Finally, the Holistic Model (Area 29) adheres almost literally to the text of the call, reserving maximum discretion for the committee.

From a CoARA perspective, the most aligned approaches are those that preserve peer judgment and avoid reducing the assessment to a numerical decomposition that can constrain deliberation. When commissions are asked to consider the candidate's contribution in a contextual, integrated, and holistic way, they are better positioned to assess quality in a nuanced manner. By contrast, when criteria are broken down into rigid, pre-determined sub-weights, the system becomes structural and mechanical, moving away from the call's mandate for a collegial, reasoned judgment and restricting disciplinary interpretation. A clear example of this weighted rigidity is found in Area 30 (Sciences of Historical-Cultural Heritage), which caps internal scores by allocating a maximum of 15 points to the overall career, 5 points to alignment with strategic positioning, and 5 points to contribution and impact on the Institution's missions. By assigning up to 60% of the total

score, this approach may in some cases outweigh the immediate scientific relevance of individual contributions. This effect does not necessarily derive from the design of the framework itself, but rather from the way specific criteria are operationalized within disciplinary areas. Similarly, Area 04 (Production Systems and Civil Engineering) introduces a fixed percentage breakdown among the three dimensions (e.g., 40%–40%–20%), adopting an analytical approach that directly contrasts with the holistic nature of the intended evaluation.

Another highly critical pattern concerns the potential tension with CoARA principles through the explicit use of bibliometric information. While responsible assessment dictates that such indicators should play at most a contextual role and must not dominate the judgment, explicit references to citation counts or h-index-type indicators appear formally in some evaluation criteria. One of the most evident and well-documented misalignments occurs in Area 09 (Neurosciences); despite the call demanding a qualitative, reasoned judgment on the overall contribution, its specific criteria formally insert the H-index and total citation count as determining evaluation parameters. This imbalance between context and proxy highlights how numbers can inherently misalign a process designed for qualitative depth. Conversely, it is equally important to highlight the positive evaluative choices that best interpret the spirit of the call and align with modern assessment standards. Areas 01, 06, and 24 explicitly identify the evaluation of multidisciplinary as an autonomous fourth dimension, ensuring that this cornerstone requirement of the competition is systematically weighed. Furthermore, Areas 10, 14, and 24 translate the three core dimensions into concrete indicators of managerial and strategic autonomy. By evaluating activities ranging from fund-raising capabilities and the creation of spin-offs to structured roles in foreign institutions, these areas faithfully reflect the advanced profile expected of a Senior Researcher.

Section 3: scientific perspective and potential

Section 3, with its maximum value of 5 points, carries the lowest specific weight in the competition, yet it is uniquely designed as a genuinely forward-looking and prospective evaluation. The call explicitly mandated a reasoned judgment on the innovative aspects and future benefits the candidate could bring to the Institution, the scientific community,

and the country. Overall, this section shows the strongest coherence with a qualitative approach, evaluating future potential rather than merely past output, and the vast majority of the 35 areas adhered faithfully to this mandate. The most prevalent model combines three core evaluative elements: the clarity of the candidate's scientific and technical vision and objectives, the feasibility of the proposed future activities, and the capacity to adapt to new research and technological directions. Several areas enrich this core with dimensions of strategic relevance. For instance, Area 04 and Area 33 require strict relevance to CNR research themes; Areas 01, 14, and 24 place a premium on multidisciplinary and the capacity to integrate into broader international project networks; and Areas 20 and 22 assess the organic nature of the research plan alongside its prospects for future success. Furthermore, a significant group of areas, including 17, 27, and 29, opted for a purely holistic model, delegating the collegial assessment to the commission in broad terms of innovativeness, feasibility, and potential impact without any further fragmentation of the score. This structured yet transparent approach is highly compatible with CoARA-oriented assessment because it defines qualitative expectations without over-specifying the scoring mechanics, ensuring that the commission retains the necessary space for peer review and integrated, contextual judgment.

In stark contrast to this widespread alignment, a problematic reliance on proxies occurs in Area 28 (Biodiversity, Ecosystems, and Biological Resources), where the past was effectively used as a surrogate for the future. While the call strictly required an evaluation of forward-looking potential, Area 28 introduced explicit criteria that measured past performance instead, namely the candidate's historical productivity—expressed as the average number of ISI-indexed publications per year over the last five years—and their past capacity to attract funding from competitive projects, particularly international ones. This structural deviation may limit the prospective nature of the section, shifting the focus back to traditional metrics and retrospective proxies instead of evaluating the candidate's strategic vision and adaptability.

Section 4: professional path

Section 4 represents the curricular portion with the lowest specific weight in the competition (5 points), yet it possesses the highest conceptual specificity: the call explicitly

mandated that it assesses professional experiences and competencies not already captured or valued in the previous sections. The principle of non-duplication is the logical foundation and the very “raison d'être” of this section. Where this principle is ignored, the section loses its distinctive, differentiating function and transforms into an improper evaluative supplement.

The areas that best interpreted this mandate are those that focused on elements genuinely uncovered by prior sections. For instance, the so-called Internationalized Model (Areas 01, 08, 10, 21, 24, 31, 34) concentrates its evaluation on external experience, international exposure, pre-CNR activities at public or private institutions, and technology transfer initiatives not already accounted for. Similarly, the Managerial Model (Areas 03, 04, 05, 19, 25, 26, 32, 33) evaluates the quality and variety of managerial and organizational competencies, the soft skills, viewing them as a personal expression derived from practical experience rather than a mere list of formal roles. Area 14 (Forestry, Wood, and Environment) offers perhaps the most detailed and appropriate catalog for this section, valuing the quality, continuity, and interdisciplinarity of professional experience alongside the acquisition of autonomy, fundraising capabilities, public engagement, entrepreneurial skills, and foreign exposure. When used in this manner, these professional elements complement the research record without redundancies, successfully maintaining a clear separation between sections and preserving the intended logic of non-duplication, which is crucial in a competition where each phase carries a distinct purpose and weight.

Conversely, the analysis shows that several areas introduce criteria that create significant distortions by overlapping with elements already extensively evaluated in Sections 2 and 3. By failing to maintain this structural boundary, these sectors allow for excessive genericness and evaluative duplication, compromising the section's distinct role.

Following these curricular components, the interview stage appears to be the section most consistently aligned with qualitative, responsible assessment principles across all 35 areas. The criteria here focus squarely on scientific maturity, clarity, autonomy, vision, and strategic coherence. Crucially, no area appears to rely on bibliometric indicators during this final stage, which stands as a highly positive sign. The interview is thus successfully utilized as a space for direct peer interaction, where the candidate's capacity for scientific

reasoning, oral communication, and future planning can be evaluated in an integrated, nuanced, and unconstrained manner.

DISCUSSION

The comparative analysis of the evaluation criteria adopted across the 35 competition areas allows for a comprehensive overview of the problematic reliance on proxies, their practical implications, and the pathways toward potential harmonization. The findings suggest that the CNR competition contains a substantial number of elements compatible with CoARA-oriented assessment, but its implementation differs significantly across disciplinary areas, shaped heavily by distinct traditions that define the operational meaning of quality. The clearest distinction emerges between the humanities/social sciences and the scientific/technological domains. In the humanities and social sciences, books, monographs, critical editions, and scholarly sources are treated as natural units of assessment, reflecting a stronger alignment with content-based, contextual, and output-sensitive evaluation. In the scientific and technological areas, while patents, software, datasets, and technological outputs are increasingly recognized alongside traditional articles, several sectors still blend this responsible expansion of outputs with a persistent reliance on bibliometric proxies, particularly for journal articles.

Crucially, the identified distortions are not random; they tend to converge toward an implicit ideal candidate profile—that of a traditional academic researcher with long seniority, high bibliometric productivity in top-tier journals, and a predominantly mono-institutional career path. This profile is exactly what the call, in its stated intentions and adherence to CoARA, aimed at de-privilege. The practical consequences of this misalignment are threefold. On an individual level, candidates with applied, multidisciplinary, or non-linear profiles, such as those with periods spent abroad, experiences in private institutions, or a strong output of prototypes and technical reports, are structurally penalized not because of the quality of their scientific contribution, but due to the rigid evaluative choices of specific committees. On an institutional level, the fragmentation of criteria across areas creates unequal treatment for candidates with similar profiles based solely on their competition area. On a regulatory level, certain specific choices, most notably the formal introduction of the H-index in Area 09 and journal

quartiles in Area 13, suggest that the practical application of evaluation criteria appears only partially aligned with the broader principles adopted at the institutional level.

This systemic variance does not imply that one disciplinary group is uniformly superior to the other but rather highlights that the most robust assessment designs are those that successfully combine qualitative peer judgment, recognition of diverse outputs, and explicit attention to context. When an evaluation framework is broken down into overly rigid sub-weights, it minimizes the space for nuanced evaluation; conversely, when it is entirely open without clear orientation, it can generate excessive heterogeneity. The most constructive path lies between these two extremes: criteria must be transparent but not mechanically restrictive, broad but not vague, and discipline-sensitive while remaining coherent with shared institutional principles.

Based on this diagnostic framework, three general observations emerge alongside concrete lines of intervention for a future harmonization of the evaluation system. First, CoARA principles are genuinely visible within the competition, particularly in the structural opening toward diverse outputs and within qualitative sections like the interview and the forward-looking phase. However, there remains an uneven, persistent use of journal-based and citation-based proxies across the scientific and technological domains. In several areas, journal-based indicators and bibliometric information play a more prominent role than recommended within CoARA frameworks, reflecting differences in how responsible metrics are interpreted across disciplinary context. Second, the holistic nature of the reasoned judgment in Sections 2 and 3 must be strictly preserved by eliminating the fixed internal weightings that mechanically constrain the committee's qualitative discretion. Third, the boundaries between sections must be protected more clearly to uphold the logical principle of non-duplication, ensuring each part of the competition serves its intended evaluative function without overlapping, and requiring committees to explicitly justify how the criteria in Section 4 isolate experiences distinct from previous phases. Finally, there must be an explicit, cross-cutting recognition of all product types (P1–P11) with differentiated but strictly non-zero-point caps. Valuing the multiplicity of research contributions, from journal articles to prototypes, software, and technical reports, remains the fundamental requirement to align the institution with its commitment to recognize all diverse forms of participation in scientific knowledge.

CONCLUSION

The CNR senior Researcher competition provides an informative and highly relevant case study for examining how international research assessment reform principles, such as those championed by CoARA, are translated into a real-world evaluation process across diverse disciplinary areas. The analysis demonstrates that the structural framework of the call contains all the necessary elements for a qualitative, pluralistic, and progressive evaluation. The fundamental challenge, therefore, lies not within the regulatory design of the call itself, but within its practical implementation and interpretation by the individual judging committees.

As it stands, this framework includes many elements highly compatible with responsible research assessment, particularly where the criteria remain qualitative, context-sensitive, and open to diverse forms of output. At the same time, the comparative data indicates substantial variation across areas regarding the use of bibliometric proxies, the internal weighting of criteria, and the degree of disciplinary specificity. The main contribution of this report is to demonstrate that alignment with CoARA is not a simple binary condition; rather, it is best understood as a spectrum shaped by disciplinary context, output traditions, and the practical design of specific assessment criteria. Humanities and social science areas tend to display a more natural, robust alignment with content-based evaluation. Conversely, scientific and technological areas more frequently attempt a hybrid approach, combining qualitative assessment with entrenched bibliometric or journal-based structures. A prime example of this uneven implementation can be seen in how the author's individual contribution is assessed. Ideally, the candidate's specific role should be consistently weighed (e.g., allocating a fixed proportion like 0.4 points out of 3 across the board) and applied homogeneously to all research products. Instead, current practices often allow individual contributions to be severely undervalued or entirely ignored when dealing with "non-conventional" outputs, creating an unfair discrepancy between product types.

Ultimately, achieving a fair and harmonized evaluation system does not require a complete overhaul of the existing regulatory framework. Instead, it demands a more rigorous, centralized oversight to ensure absolute compliance with the principles already declared in the institutional mandate. Future harmonization efforts must benefit from clearer, binding

guidance that enforces a strictly qualitative peer-review process, guarantees the meaningful recognition of a multiplicity of research contributions, protects the clear distinction among evaluation sections, and ensures the definitive abandonment of metrics that CoARA has deemed inappropriate.

Future work should integrate outcome-based validation.

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APPENDIX

The table provides an English comparative synthesis of the criteria used in Section 1 across the 35 disciplinary areas of the CNR senior Researcher competition, based on the official competition documentation made publicly available through the CNR URP archive.

Area	Journal articles	Books / chapters	Author role	Other relevant outputs
01	Max 2 points by journal ranking (Q1-Q4).	Books max 2; chapters 1.	Max 1 point.	Patents max 2.
02	Max 3 points by ranking (Q1-Q4) and context.	Books 1; chapters 1.	Max 1 point.	Patents max 2.
03	Excellent = 2; Good = 1; Insufficient = 0.	Monographs max 2 plus author role.	First / last / main author = 0.5.	Patents: international 3; national 2.
04	Originality 30%, venue 25%, method 10%, impact 15%, contribution 20%.	International ISBN 3; national ISBN 2.	Position-based multipliers.	Patents: licensed 3; filed 2.
05	Relevance, originality, role, impact, max 3.	Books max 2.5; chapters 2.5.	Included in product criteria.	Patents max 2.5.
06	Journal rank Q1-Q4, max 2.	Volumes: relevance/impact max 3.	Leading author 1; co-author 0.5.	Patents: international 3; national 1.5.
07	Impact, originality, rigor, max 1.5.	Books max 0.7; chapters 0.8.	First / corresponding / last = 1.	Patents max 3, based on international relevance.
08	Ranking Q1-Q4, up to 2.	Monographs max 1; role max 1.	First / last = 1; second = 0.5.	Patents: international 2.5; national 1.5.

Area	Journal articles	Books / chapters	Author role	Other relevant outputs
09	Impact scale: excellent 3, very good 2.5, good 2.	Monographs max 2.	First / last x1.0; others x0.9.	Patents: granted 2.5; filed 1.
10	Rank Q1-Q4 plus impact, max 2.	Books max 3; chapters 2.	Max 1 point.	Patents: international 2.5; national 1.5.
11	Q1 = 1.5; Q2 = 1; Q3 = 0.5; Q4 = 0.2.	English-language books with ISBN only, 2 points.	First / last / corresponding = 1; others = 0.2.	Software only if formally registered, 0.5.
12	Relevance / quality, max 1.5.	Monographs / treatises, max 1.5.	Max 1.5 for books; 1 for articles.	Patents max 3.
13	Ranking Q1-Q4, max 1.5.	Books max 3; chapters max 2.	Max 1 point.	Patents max 3.
14	Journal value via Scimago, max 1.5.	Relevance / quality, max 1.5.	First / corresponding = 1; others = 0.4.	Software: international 2; national 1.
15	Originality, innovation, impact, role, max 3.	International monograph 2.5; national 1.	Based on bibliometric parameters.	International granted patents 3.
16	Relevance 1 plus citation impact 0.5.	Relevance 0.5 plus impact 0.5.	First / last / corresponding = 1; alphabetical = 0.9.	Patents only if granted, max 3.
17	Relevance 0.5 + impact 0.5 + originality 0.5 + multidisciplinary 0.5.	Editorial placement max 1.	First / corresponding / last max 1.	Patents max 3.
18	Quality 1 + impact 1 + originality 1.	Quality 1 + impact 1 + originality 1.	Role max 1.	Software max 3.

Area	Journal articles	Books / chapters	Author role	Other relevant outputs
19	Relevance / impact / method, up to 2.	Books / treatises up to 3.	Author order and coherence considered.	Patents: international 3; national 2.
20	Excellent 3; very good 2.5; good 1.5.	Excellent 2; very good 1.5.	Evaluated analytically.	Patents max 3.
21	Relevance, impact, originality, role, max 3.	Same parameters as articles, max 2.	Included in product criteria.	Patents max 3.
22	Originality 1.2 + international impact 1.2 + multidisciplinary 0.6 + societal value 0.6.	Originality 1.2 + impact 1.2 + role 1.0.	Signature position and CV considered.	Patents max 3.
23	Relevance / impact / contribution, max 2.	Relevance / impact / contribution, max 2.	Included in relevance.	Patents: international 3; national 2.
24	Excellent 1; very good 0.75 plus impact/role 2.	Leading author max 1.5.	Specific contribution max 2, together with impact.	Patents: international 2; national 1.5.
25	Relevance 1.2 + venue 0.6 + role 0.6 + originality 0.6.	Same structure.	Up to 0.6.	Patents max 3.
26	Q1 = 2; Q2 = 1.5; Q3 = 1 plus significance 0.5 and contribution 0.5.	International volume with DOI 2; national 1.	Up to 0.5.	Open software 1; closed software 0.5.
27	Relevance 1 + originality 0.5 + impact 0.5 + role 0.75.	Relevance 1 + originality 0.5 + impact 1 + role 0.25.	First / corresponding / last = 0.75.	Patents max 3.

Area	Journal articles	Books / chapters	Author role	Other relevant outputs
28	Venue/citations 1.5 + societal value 0.5 + originality 0.5 + role 1.	Co-holder 1.5; sole holder 2.	First / corresponding / last = 1; others = 0.2.	Patents: international 3; national 1.5.
29	Venue 0.5 + impact 0.4 + originality 0.4 + multidisciplinary 0.3 + peer review 1.	Similar parameters to articles, max 3.	First / sole author 0.4; fewer than 10 authors 0.2.	Open software 1; closed software 0.5.
30	Relevance 1.2 + venue 0.6 + role 0.6 + originality 0.6.	Same parameters, max 3.	Up to 0.6.	Patents max 3.
31	Excellent 1; very good 0.75 across four parameters.	Overall quality max 2.	Included among the four parameters, max 1.	Patents: international 3; national 1.5.
32	Quality 1.2 + originality 1.2 + role 0.6.	Quality 1.2 + originality 1.2 + role 0.6.	Up to 0.6.	Patents: international 3; national 2.
33	ANVUR Class A = 2.7; Scientific Journal = 2.5.	Series with editorial board 3; others 2.5.	Included in overall quality.	Critical editions / sources 1.5.
34	Excellent 1; very good 0.75 across four parameters.	Overall quality max 3.	Included among the four parameters, max 1.	Patents max 2.5.
35	Included in relevance, max 1.5 if Class A.	Original monograph / critical edition 2.	Single author 1; multiple authors 0.5.	Publication of unpublished sources 2.